

Design of a Four-Wheeled Inner Pipeline Inspection Robot

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Abstract: The field of autonomous robotics is growing rapidly. Nowadays, robots are found everywhere, ranging from homes, hospitals to industries and military operations. In this thesis, we present a six-wheel inner pipeline inspection robot designed for safety, security, efficient and accurate data collection various inner pipe environments. The robot incorporates a differential drive system which consists of two independent driving wheels, the transmission device is a two-stage conical gear reducer unpowered by a DC motor, the third wheel is a caster wheel ensuring the balanced of the robot. The control system of the robot comprises an Arduino microcontroller that is connected to a Raspberry Pi, serving as the central processing unit. The Raspberry Pi is equipped with the Robot Operating System (ROS), a powerful framework that facilitates seamless integration of sensor data and motor control. The ROS enables the robot to communicate with and coordinate the actions of various hardware components, ensuring efficient and reliable operation. The robot is equipped with a LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) sensor, which utilizes laser technology to accurately measure distances and create detailed maps of the environment. This allows the robot to navigate autonomously while avoiding obstacles and efficiently planning inspection routes. Additionally, a camera is integrated into the system, providing visual input for object recognition, environmental awareness, and capturing images or video data for further analysis. This information is then processed by the Raspberry Pi running ROS, enabling the robot to make informed decisions and autonomously navigate through complex environments. The inspection robot is capable of collecting real-time data during its autonomous missions, enabling efficient and data-driven decision-making for applications such as surveillance, monitoring, and inspection tasks. The system's flexibility and adaptability make it suitable for a wide range of inspection scenarios, contributing to improved efficiency and productivity in various industries and applications.

Keywords: Pipeline inspection robot, Four-wheel robot, Autonomous robots, IPIR, Lidar

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Introduction

Pipelines have been a major component for many industries that keep the world running. Water supply, oil and gas, power plants, and even beverage manufacturers, among others, are some of the industries that rely on working pipelines. However, due to agents such as aging and physical damage from other sources, defects can occur in these piping systems. Inspection of pipeline is an important task so as to ensure there are no defects that may eventually lead to problems such as leakage, which in the worst-case scenario may lead to a fatal hazard such as an explosion.[1]

The main concern in designing a mobile platform or robot for traversing through pipelines is how to tackle varying pipe geometry such as pipe branch, changing diameters, and pipe elbows [2]. There are a number of robot designs that feature advantages and disadvantages when utilized to traverse through these types of pipe geometry. Pipe branch however presents a larger obstacle for the design when compared to pipe elbows and changing diameters. Varying diameters in a pipeline are still a linear path and will only pose a problem to some robot designs where their working principle is based on the internal diameter of the pipe such as the wall press robot. Similarly, pipe elbows are also a linear path for the robot to traverse through and will only need little extra consideration for the design. Pipe branches, on the other hand, does not present a linear path and may be geometrically complex [1,2]. [1]

Inspection procedures for underground structures have improved the efficiency of the excavation work. A thorough understanding of the current status underground is obtained first to allow high-speed excavation to the target pipe while avoiding other underground items. This procedure would be adequate if improving excavation speed was all that was needed, but it does not reduce excavation time enough. What is needed is a review of the exterior surface inspection method itself. In addition to outer surface inspection, another procedure currently in practice is interior surface inspection. Interior surface inspections require excavating a pit just large enough to insert the inspection equipment, so the work can be performed much more efficiently in terms of both cost and time. Since most pipes are laid under roads, this procedure offers the general public the advantages that less excavation means that less road surface area torn up and time needed for the work, and neither pedestrian nor vehicular detours are necessary.[3]

Research Significance

Inspection robots hold a special place in the business due to their distinct advantages as technology develops and matures. For stance:

- **Efficiency:** Inspection robots can carry out repetitive operations faster and with greater accuracy than humans, increasing production and efficiency across a variety of industries.
- **Safety:** Inspection robots can perform tasks in hazardous environments, such as nuclear power plants, chemical factories, or oil rigs, without endangering human life.
- **Cost-effective:** Inspection robots can reduce labor costs since they can work around the clock and do not require breaks or sick leave.
- **Data collection:** Inspection robots are equipped with sensors that can collect data and perform real-time analysis, enabling operators to make informed decisions.
- **Maintenance:** Inspection robots can be used for preventive maintenance, allowing operators to identify and address issues before they become critical, which can reduce equipment downtime and maintenance costs.

Research Status

German ROSEN is a leading global supplier of cutting-edge solutions in all fields of the integrity process chain. Its product pipeline pig can operate in high-speed flowing fluid, as shown in Figure 1. It provides complete multi-physics all-round detection such as magnetic flux leakage detection, optical detection, ultrasonic detection for oil and gas pipelines.[4]

Figure 1-1: Pipeline Inspection Pig

S. G. Roh of Sungkyunkwan University in South Korea and others have jointly developed MRINSPECT series of pipeline robots [2,5]. They have the ability to pass through elbow pipes, and also have the ability to turn pipes. They can choose to turn during driving, and pass through urban gas pipelines with branch pipes. MRINSPECT IV in this series of robots, as shown in Figure 3 below, is mainly composed of body frame, drive module and electric coupler (CCD).[4] The radial dimension of the robot is 85-109 mm, and the axial dimension is 150 mm. Relying on the body weight of 0.7 kg, it can generate 9.8N traction force and 0.15 m/s travel speed.

Ho Moon Kim et al. applied a multi-axis gear differential mechanism to MRINSPECT VI [6], which solved the problem that the speed of the robot wheels could not be accurately controlled during the rotation of the inner wall of the pipe, resulting in the uncoordinated rotation of the wheels, thus consuming unnecessary energy and causing irreparable damage to the robot.[4]

Figure 1-2: Pipeline robot of Sungkyunkwan University in South Korea

As shown in Figure 3, it is a pipeline detection robot with a linkage mechanical clutch developed by Young-Sik Kwon and Byung-Ju Yi of Hanyang University in South Korea [7]. The total length of the body is 122 mm, the minimum external diameter is 90 mm, and the maximum extension is 110 mm. The weight of the robot is 189 grams. The robot operates in a pipeline with a pipe diameter of 100 mm at a speed of 14 cm/s. The robot is small and flexible. The experimental results show that it can smoothly pass through the 90-degree elbow. It can detect the pipeline through its own lighting system and camera, and can successfully recover it through the external control system. However, the tractive force of the robot is too small for external power supply, so the detection distance is limited, and it is not suitable for the detection of long oil and gas pipelines. [4]

Figure 1-3: Pipe robot of Hanyang University in South Korea

Research status in China

China is not lacking behind, in fact While AGVs and AMRs are utilized around the world, the greatest drivers of development are coming from China and the US. In Feb. 2014 A circular inspection robot goes on patrol at the 500-kilovolt Doushan Substation in Wuxi City, east China's Jiangsu province. [8]

Figure 1-4: Substation robot

The TVIS 1000 train bottom inspection robots developed by Shenhao robotics, this robot is used in the daily maintenance work of the train. It solves the problems of heavy task, difficult to detect, leakage inspection.[8]

Figure 1-5: TVIS 1000 robot

Summary: This chapter has proven the important significance and value of inner-pipeline inspection robot. According to the domestic and foreign analysis of the development of the field, combine with some analysed cases, we could notice how prominent it actually is and it will continue to grow as further research are still being conducted.

Project Assignment and Methodology: The field of robotics has countless applications in daily living. In order to incorporate robots into every aspect of our everyday lives, researchers are making enormous advancements in the field of robotics at the same time. Robots for inspecting pipelines are one use of robotics. Pipelines are now a necessary component in the transmission of liquids and gases. They now need to be inspected and monitored on a regular basis, but since pipelines are typically placed in extremely remote locations, doing these jobs traditionally can be costly.

Figure 2-1 Initially designed robot

Design Requirements

Table 2-1 Table of main technical indicators

Project	unit	parameter
Machine Weight	kg	10 - 20
Driving speed	m/s	0.5 - 1.0
Driving positioning accuracy	mm	±10
Length, width	mm	300 X 300
Power supply	V, Ah	Lithium iron phosphate battery 36, 30
Communication mode		Wireless
Navigation mode		Trackless and Autonomous

Different types of pipeline inspection robots:

The PIG type utilises a launcher and receiver to move inside the pipeline under fluid pressure. The walking or legged type uses legs, and these legs mimic the movement of a leg to walk inside the pipeline. The caterpillar type moves inside pipelines on tracked wheels, enabling them to maintain contact with the pipeline's inner surface under variable conditions. The wheeled type robot is simple in mechanism and uses wheels to move in the pipeline. The wall-press type uses the contact force between the robot and pipeline surface to move in the pipeline. The inchworm type uses the robot's gripping force to move through the pipeline. The screw type robot has wheels inclined at an angle to replicate the motion of a screw to move inside a pipeline. Each category has its own set of benefits and limitations. The PIG type struggles to turn at sharp bends. The screw-type has a complex steering mechanism and finds difficulty in back driving. The inchworm type has less traction force than the other types. The wall-press type has high friction that can harm the pipeline structure and is challenging to steer, and the walking type has a complicated mechanism and gets stuck when the mechanism fails. As a result, of all the types, the wheeled type IPIR is best suited for in-pipeline inspection because

they only have a traditional limitation of pipe slippage, which is kept under control by appropriate design and development. This paper focuses on wheeled type In-Pipe Inspection Robots and their application in various pipeline inspections. Even though the screw-type employs wheels, it does not fall under the wheeled type. Hence it will not be discussed in this review. In comparison to other types of in-pipe robots, the wheeled in-pipe inspection robot has the following advantages: It is simple in mechanism, there is less friction between the robot and pipe wall, mobility inside the pipeline is high, and crawls through horizontal, vertical, curved, branched and varying diameter pipes, it back-drives with ease, lighter and smaller robot is achievable through proper design, manoeuvres through pipelines with a lesser inner diameter starting from 40 mm, overcomes obstacle inside pipelines, it is modular in design, and there are possibilities to employ different types of wheels, etc. [9]

Figure 2-2 Different In-Pipe Inspection Robots: (a) PIG, (b) Caterpillar, (c) Inchworm, (d) Screw, (e) Walking, (f) Wheel, (g) Wall-Press [9]

Locomotion types used in wheeled type in-pipe inspection robot (IPIR)

Figure 2-3 Classification of wheels based on their use in pipeline robots.

Two wheeled wall-pressed type IPIR:

The two-wheeled wall-pressed type IPIR uses two wheels placed symmetrically at an angle of 180 degrees apart from each other, as shown in Fig. 2.4. It reduces the area occupied by the robot inside the pipeline. This robot uses a two-wheel chain mechanism to move inside the pipeline. The two-chain mechanism pushes the two wheels against the inner surface of the pipeline to gain stability for moving inside the pipeline. [9]

Figure 2-4 Two wheeled wall-pressed type IPIR [9]

Three wheeled wall-pressed type IPIR:

The three-wheeled wall-pressed type IPIR is one of the most used types of hybrid locomotion. It is the combination of wheeled type and wall-press type, as shown in Fig. 2.5. The three-wheeled wall-pressed IPIR uses three wheels placed at an angle of 120 degrees symmetrically apart from each other to crawl through the pipelines. The robot uses spring, adaptive linkage, four-bar, five-bar and parallelogram to make the arm adjust according to the inner shape and diameter of the pipeline. The three wheels press against the inner surface of the pipeline to stabilize themselves and move inside the pipeline. In this type of design, there is a possibility of motion singularity (loss of contact between robot and pipe) occurring inside pipelines. [9]

Figure 2-5 Prototypes of three wheeled wall-pressed type IPIR. (a) Spring Mechanism, (b) Adaptive Mechanism, (c) Four-Bar, Five-Bar and Parallelogram Mechanism.[9]

Supporting wheeled type IPIR:

The wheeled type IPIR that uses standard wheels to crawl inside the pipelines adds a supporting wheel on the top of the robot to form the supporting wheeled type IPIR, as shown in Fig. 2.6. This type overcomes the limitations of wheeled type IPIR, which cannot climb vertical pipes and can only pass through horizontal and slightly inclined pipelines. The robot uses springs to make the supporting wheels touch the inner surface of the pipelines. This support helps the robot to move through horizontal and vertical pipelines. The limitation of this design is that it is difficult to pass through branched pipes.[9]

Figure 2-6 Prototypes of supporting wheeled type IPIR. (a) Semi-Autonomous Robot, (b) PIRSMA. [9]

Multilink-Articulated wheeled type IPIR:

The articulated wheeled type IPIR employs the robot's joints to form a V-shape so that the wheels at the end of the joints press against the pipeline's inner surface, as seen in Fig. 2.7. This shape helps the robot crawl through the pipeline with a body bent like an inchworm. The robots use motor-actuated joints and torsion springs to form a V-shape structure that allows them to clamp inside pipelines. Its limitation comes when the inner diameter of the pipeline increases, as this type of robot requires an increase in the length and number of drives used to form a V-shape so that it can gain stability for motion in vertical pipes.[9]

Figure 2-7 Prototypes of articulated wheeled type IPIR. a) AIRO, b) PIRATE.[9]

Power Selection

Option 1: Stepper motor.

They use a stator with coils and a rotor with teeth to create a magnetic field that moves the rotor in tiny increments. They can be accurately controlled by adjusting the timing and sequencing of the electrical impulses sent to the coils, and they move in exact steps by activating the coils in a sequence to attract the rotor teeth magnetically. Stepper motors are employed in robotics, CNC machines, 3D printers, and other applications that call for exact positioning or motion control.

Figure 2-8 Detail assembly of a stepper motor

Option 2: DC motor

They have a rotor with brushes and a commutator that supply the rotor's electrical connections. The rotor rotates because of a magnetic field created by permanent magnets or coils inside the stator. DC motors use the interaction between the rotor's current and the stator's magnetic field to transform electrical energy into mechanical energy. Power tools, pumps, fans, and other devices requiring variable speed or torque employ DC motors.

Figure 2-9 Detail assembly of a DC motor

Option 3: AC motor

To create a revolving magnetic field that induces current in the rotor and causes it to spin, they have a stator with coils and a rotor with bars or coils. By adjusting the frequency, voltage, or phase of the power source, AC motors may transform electrical energy into mechanical energy through the interplay of the rotor's induced current and the stator's revolving magnetic field. Applications requiring great power and efficiency, such as electric cars, HVAC systems, and industrial machines, employ AC motors.

Figure 2-10 Detail assembly of an AC motor

From the analysis of the above considerations, the stepper motors are ideal for precise positioning and motion control, DC motors are suitable for variable speed and torque applications, and AC motors are best for high power and efficiency applications. The DC motor is chosen in this design.

Analysis of Transmission System Scheme

A suitable transmission needs only guarantee the design's stability, dependability in a range of conditions, and address concerns like weight and size as well as maintenance and repair. Meeting the aforementioned condition is quite challenging, and doing so might result in higher expenses. We must thus choose a suitable design in accordance with the design function.

Option 1: Single-stage cylindrical gear reducer

The transmission speed of the single-stage cylindrical gear reducer is high, and it has an easy-to-assemble and maintain compact structure. Although it is extensively used, has a broad rate range, and has a flexible axis layout that allows it to be positioned horizontally, vertically, and up and down, its transmission ratio needs to be bigger and fulfil the criteria of this design.

Figure 2-11 Single stage cylindrical gear reducer

Option 2: Single-stage screw reducer

The single-stage screw reducer has a compact structure and is easy to assemble and repair. This shape of the single-stage screw reducer structure, this formula is suitable for operation with small loads and intermittent work.

Figure 2-12 Single stage screw gear reducer

Option 3: Conical-cylindrical gear reducer

In this structural form of circular push-cylindrical gear reducer, the push gear should be arranged in the high-speed stage, and the bevel gear should be arranged in the high-speed stage.

Figure 2-13 Two stage conical-cylindrical gear reducer

According to the above analysis the conical-cylindrical gear reducer is chosen in this design.

Kinematics analysis of the differential steering mechanism

Differential drive or differential steering is the simplest locomotion system encountered in a inner pipeline inspection robot. The differential locomotion system is most often found in two-wheeled robots and consists of two wheels mounted on a common rotating axis actuated by two individual servomotors.

Figure 2-14 differential steering mechanism analysis

With a differential steering locomotion system, a robot can realize a rotational movement around an axis perpendicular to a point contained by the axis of the two traction wheels. By changing the angular velocities of the two traction wheels, the direction of rotation can be changed. The angular velocities of the two wheels should respect the mathematical equation presented below:

$$v_r = \omega \times \left(R + \frac{l}{2}\right), v_l = \omega \times \left(R - \frac{l}{2}\right)$$

In the above formula, v_l characterizes the angular velocity for the left wheel and v_r characterizes the angular velocity for the right wheel. R describes the radius of the circular path travelled by the center of the robot. ω the angular velocity of the wheel, and l the distance between the two traction wheels. The orientation of the robot is described by θ angle. By solving the system of equations one can obtain the solutions presented below:

$$R = \frac{[l \times (v_r + v_l)]}{[2 \times (v_r - v_l)]}, \quad \omega = (v_r - v_l)/l$$

If the two angular velocities are equal $v_r = v_l$, the radius R is infinite. In this case, the robot will move in a straight line. If the two angular velocities have the same value but different direction $v_r = -v_l$, the distance R is 0, and the robot will rotate around a vertical axis placed in the middle of the I axis. For different values for v_l and v_r , the robot will move on a circular path of radius R with respect to the center of curvature CC.

Summary

To guarantee effective and efficient performance, the inner pipeline inspection robot's suggested design includes a number of crucial elements. The robot will have a revolving camera system, a conical cylindrical gearbox, a differential drive system with a caster wheel, and a DC motor.

Using a DC motor has several benefits, including small size, high torque production, and accurate speed control. It makes it possible for the robot's control system to be seamlessly integrated, allowing for precise and easy manoeuvrability. The use of a conical cylindrical gearbox will further improve the motor's performance. With the gear reduction mechanism this gearbox offers, torque output may be increased while motor speed can be decreased. It guarantees the best possible power transfer from the engine to the wheels, allowing the robot to manoeuvre around obstacles and perform at a higher level of efficiency. A differential drive system, which makes use of two independently controlled drive wheels, will be included in the robot. Because each wheel in this design may revolve at a different speed, accurate turning and manoeuvring are made possible. The design will have a caster wheel to provide stability and balance. By offering stability and support, the caster wheel keeps the robot upright during sharp bends and abrupt motions.

Combining a differential drive system with a caster wheel, a conical cylindrical gearbox, and a DC motor would enable the mobile robot to operate steadily and dependably while traversing a variety of terrains and carrying out complex manoeuvres. Overall, this combination of the design guarantees the best possible performance, adaptability, and control, which makes the mobile robot ideal for a variety of activities and applications.

Design of the gearbox

The figure below shows the inside of the pipeline inspection robot chassis which contain: the motor, the gearbox, the battery, the four driving wheels, the two rollers.

Figure 3-1 Inside of inspection robot chassis

Selection of a motor

It is known that the inner pipeline inspection robot weight is 20 kilograms, The percentage of gravity borne by the four driving wheels of the robot will depend on several factors such as the weight distribution of the robot, the position of the center of gravity, and the angle of the robot's body relative to the ground. However, assuming that the weight of the robot is slightly evenly distributed, and that the robot is on a level surface, each of the two front driving wheels will bear more than fifty percent (50%) of the robot's weight. We suppose that the two driving wheels bear seventy percent (70%) of gravity, each front wheel carry thirty five percent (35%) and the caster carry thirty percent (30%). The rolling friction coefficient between the wheel and the ground by Ron Kurtus vary between 0.5~1, and the diameter of the driving wheel 100mm.

1. Maximal Tension

Total force due to gravity acting on the robots: $F_G = 20 \times 9.8 = 196\text{N}$

The force borne by the two driving wheels: $F_f = 70\% \times 196 = 137.2\text{N}$

The force borne by the two driving wheels: $F_r = 30\% \times 196 = 58.8\text{N}$

Therefore, the force borne by each of the two front driving wheels is approximately 137.2N, while the force borne by the rear wheel is approximately 58.8N.

For typical indoor environment with a hard, flat surface such as concrete, a reasonable range for the coefficient of friction between the driving wheel and the ground can be assumed between 0.02 to 0.05. We choose 0.02.

The overcoming friction force of the driving wheel is: $F_1 = f \times F_f = 0.02343 = 3.21\text{N}$

The overcoming friction of the rear caster wheel: $F_2 = f \times F_r = 0.02 \times 58.8 = 1.176\text{N}$

Under a certain torque, the drive wheel overcomes friction, and the steering wheel is in a driven state. The maximum tension of the mobile robot during movement is:

$$F = 2 \times F_1 + F_2 = 8.772\text{N}$$

2. Input power

According to the working requirements and working conditions, the DC motor has good starting and speed regulation performance, wide and smooth speed regulation range, and strong overload capacity. Therefore, it was decided to choose a DC motor. The efficiency of a DC motor typically ranges from 70% to 90%, depending on the motor design and operating conditions. We select 80%.

$$P_w = F \times v / \eta = 21.93N.$$

3. Transmission efficiency and total efficiency

The efficiency of each transmission component according to the Table 1-2 of the 'Mechanical Design Course Design Manual' is: $\eta_1 = 0.99$, $\eta_2 = 0.97$, $\eta_3 = 0.96$, $\eta_4 = 0.99$, $\eta_5 = 0.96$. where η_1 is the rolling bearing efficiency, η_2 is the gear transmission efficiency, and η_3 is the bevel gear efficiency, η_4 is the elastic coupling efficiency and η_5 is the roller shaft sliding efficiency. Total efficiency: $\eta = \eta_1^3 \times \eta_2 \times \eta_3 \times \eta_4 \times \eta_5 = 0.843$.

3. Output power

$$P_d = \frac{P_w}{\eta} = \frac{21.93}{0.843} = 26.014W.$$

4. Wheel speed

$$n_w = \frac{60 \times v}{\pi \times D} = \frac{60 \times 2}{\pi \times 0.12} = 318.3r/min.$$

Comprehensively considering the size, weight, price and other factors of the motor and transmission device, it was decided to choose the model HJX36RIBL100i24VX1001BM, and its parameter are as follows: V=24V, I=5.8A, torque=1.6N.m, speed=2900r/min, power=90W.

$P_d \leq P_d \text{ motor}$, the motor selected meets the requirements.

Figure 3-2 HJX36RIBL100i24VX1001BM-DC planetary gear reduction motor

Gear Transmission Design Scheme

The two stage gears of the reducer are soft surface gear. The first stage transmission adopts spur bevel gear transmission, the second stage adopt cylindrical helical gear transmission and the check scheme and design scheme adopted are contact fatigue strength design and bending fatigue strength check. Such a design structure can ensure a compact structure, and at the same time have a reliable and stable guarantee for the stability of transmission and transmission efficiency

Bevel gear transmission design calculation

1.The bevel gear transmission parameter design (known $T_1 = 0.16N.m$, $n_1 = 2900r/min$, $i_1 = 1$). The material for the big and pinions is 45-gauge steel and has an accuracy class of 8. The number of pinion teeth is generally 16~30, we select $z_1 = 30$, thus $z_2 = z_1 \times 1 = 30$

Designed according to the contact fatigue strength of the tooth surface.

Pinion index circle diameter d_{1t}

$$d_{1t} \geq \sqrt[3]{\left(\frac{Z_E}{[\sigma_H]}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{KT_1}{\psi_R(1-0.5\psi_R)^2 i_1}}$$

Parameter determination:

Load factor: $K = K_A \cdot K_V \cdot K_\alpha \cdot K_\beta$

(1) Stable transmission, obtained from Table 6-4[10] $K = 1.8$.

(2) The circumferential velocity at the initial index circle is $v = 2m/s$, $\frac{v \times z_1}{100} = 0.6$

(3) The inter-tooth load distribution coefficient $K_\alpha = 1$ is obtained from Table 14-3-31[10];

(4) Take the tooth width coefficient from Figure 6-8 $\Psi_R = 0.16$ And because there is

$$\Psi_d = \frac{\Psi_R \times \sqrt{u^2 + 1}}{2 - \Psi_R}, \Psi_d = 0.025$$

(5) Known $T_1 = 1.14N.m$

(6) node area coefficient $Z_H = 2.5$ is obtained The from Fig. 14-3-23, $\beta=0$;

(7) The elastic influence coefficient $Z_E = 389.8$ is obtained from Table 14-1-66[10];

$$Z_E Z_H = 389.8 \times 2.5 = 974.50$$

(8) Contact fatigue strength limit: $\sigma_{H \text{ lim}1} = 550 \text{ MPa}$; $\sigma_{H \text{ lim}2} = 450 \text{ MPa}$

(9) Calculate the number of stress cycles:

$$N_1 = 60 \times n_1 \times j \times L = 60 \times 2400 \times 1 \times (5 \times 300 \times 8) = 17.2 \times 10^8.$$

$$N_2 = \frac{N_1}{i_1} = \frac{1.71 \times 10^9}{3} = 5.73 \times 10^8.$$

(10) Contact fatigue life coefficient obtained according to Table 14-3-3[10]

$$K_{HN1} = 1.0, K_{HN2} = 1.0$$

The failure rate is 1%, and the safety factor $S = 1$ is obtained

$$[\sigma_H]_1 = \frac{K_{HN1} \cdot \sigma_{H \text{ lim}1}}{S} = \frac{1.0 \times 550}{1} = 550 \text{ MPa}.$$

$$[\sigma_H]_2 = \frac{K_{HN2} \cdot \sigma_{H \text{ lim}2}}{S} = \frac{1.0 \times 450}{1} = 450 \text{ MPa}.$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{take } [\sigma_H]_2 = 450 \text{ MPa}$$

Calculation :

(1) Pinion index circle diameter d_{1t}

$$\begin{aligned} d_{1t} &\geq \sqrt[3]{\left(\frac{Z_E Z_H}{[\sigma_H]}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{4KT_1}{\Psi_R \cdot (1 - 0.5\Psi_R)^2 i_1}} \\ &\geq \sqrt[3]{\left(\frac{974.5}{450}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{4 \times 1.8 \times 0.16 \times 10^3}{0.16 \times (1 - 0.5 \times 0.26)^2 \times 3}} = 23.69\text{mm}. \\ d_{1t} &= 23.69\text{mm}. \end{aligned}$$

(2) Calculate the circumferential velocity at the average index circle

$$v_m = \frac{\pi \cdot d_{m1} \cdot n_1}{60 \times 1000} = \frac{\pi \times 23.69 \times 2900}{60 \times 1000} = 3.59\text{m/s}.$$

(3) Correction of load factor

$$\frac{v_m \cdot z_1}{100} = \frac{3.59 \times 16}{100} = 0.57.$$

dynamic load factor $K_A = 1.25$, $K_V = 1.15$;

The tooth load distribution coefficient is obtained from Figure 6-17 $K_\beta = 1.875$;

$$K_t = K_A \cdot K_V \cdot K_\alpha \cdot K_\beta = 1.25 \times 1.15 \times 1 \times 1.875 = 2.795 \approx 2.80.$$

(4) Correct the trial large-end indexing circle diameter

$$d_1 = d_{1t} \cdot \sqrt[3]{\frac{K}{K_t}} = 23.69 \times \sqrt[3]{\frac{2.80}{1.8}} = 27.44\text{mm}.$$

(5) Determine the size parameters

1. Modulus determination

$$m = \frac{d_1}{z_1} = \frac{27.44}{16} = 1.53$$

normalize the modulus to $m=2$;

2. Indexing circle diameter

$$d_1 = m \times z_1 = 2 \times 30 = 60\text{mm.}$$

$$d_2 = m \times z_2 = 2 \times 30 = 60\text{mm.}$$

3. Calculate the taper pitch

$$R = \frac{m}{2} \sqrt{(z_1^2 + z_2^2)} = 32.40\text{mm}$$

4. Calculate the gear width

$$b = \Psi_R \cdot R = 0.16 \times 32.40 = 5.18\text{mm.}$$

Round, take $b_1 = b_2 = 5\text{mm}$

5. Cone angle δ

$$\delta_1 = \arctan \frac{z_1}{z_2} = \arctan \frac{30}{30} = 0^\circ.$$

$$\delta_2 = \arctan \frac{z_2}{z_1} = \arctan \frac{30}{30} = 0^\circ.$$

(4) Bevel gear transmission strength check

There is the following formula:

$$\sigma_{F1} = \frac{4KT_1}{\Psi_R(1-0.5\Psi_R)^2 z_1^2 m^3 \sqrt{i_1^2 + 1}} Y_{Fa1} Y_{Sa1} \leq [\sigma_{F1}].$$

$$\sigma_{F2} = \frac{\sigma_{F1} Y_{Fa2} Y_{Sa2}}{Y_{Fa1} Y_{Sa1}}.$$

1. Equivalent number of teeth

$$z_{v1} = \frac{z_1}{\cos \delta_1} = \frac{30}{\cos 1} = 30.$$

$$z_{v1} = \frac{z_1}{\cos \delta_1} = \frac{30}{\cos 1} = 30.$$

$$Y_{Fa1} = 2.36 \quad Y_{Sa1} = 1.59$$

$$Y_{Fa2} = 2.01 \quad Y_{Sa2} = 1.87$$

2. Calculate the allowable stress of bending fatigue:

Take the failure probability of 1%, and the safety factor $S=1$

$$[\sigma_{F1}] = \frac{K_{FN1} \sigma_{Flim1}}{S}.$$

$$[\sigma_{F2}] = \frac{K_{FN2} \sigma_{Flim2}}{S}.$$

From Figure 6-26[10] $K_{FN1} = K_{FN2} = 1$

So, $[\sigma_{F1}] = \sigma_{Flim1} = 420\text{MPa}$

$$[\sigma_{F1}] = \sigma_{Flim2} = 390\text{MPa}$$

$$\sigma_{F1} = \frac{4KT_1}{\Psi_R(1-0.5\Psi_R)^2 z_1^2 m^3 \sqrt{i_1^2 + 1}} Y_{Fa1} Y_{Sa1}.$$

$$= \frac{4 \times 1.8 \times 0.16 \times 10^3 \times 2.56 \times 1.61}{0.16 \times (1 - 0.5 \times 0.16)^2 \times 30^2 \times 2^3 \times \sqrt{1^2 + 1}} = 3.44\text{MPa.}$$

$$\sigma_{F2} = \frac{4KT_1}{\psi_R(1-0.5\psi_R)^2 z_1^2 m^3 \sqrt{i_1^2 + 1}} Y_{Fa2} Y_{Sa2}.$$

$$\sigma_{F2} = \sigma_{F1} \cdot \frac{Y_{Fa2} Y_{Sa2}}{Y_{Fa1} Y_{Sa1}} = 3.44 \times \frac{2.01 \times 1.87}{2.36 \times 1.59} = 3.44 \text{MPa}.$$

By $\sigma_{F1} < [\sigma_{F1}]$, $\sigma_{F2} < [\sigma_{F2}]$. So, meet the strength requirements.

Cylindrical gear transmission design calculation

(1) Design of cylindrical gear transmission parameters (known $T_2 = 0.46 \text{N.m}$,

$$n_2 = 322.22 \text{r/min}; i_2 = 3).$$

1. The material of big gear and pinion is 45 steels, and the accuracy grade is 8 grades.
2. The number of pinion teeth is generally 20~40, and $z_1 = 15$, is selected
3. The number of large gear teeth $z_2 = 35$. Select the helix angle ($\beta = 8^\circ \sim 25^\circ$), select the spiral angle primarily $\beta = 10^\circ$
4. The tooth width coefficient, the bearing relative gear asymmetrical arrangement check table 6-7 $\psi_d = 1.0$.

$$d_1 = \sqrt[3]{\frac{2KT_2}{\psi_d} \cdot \frac{i_2 + 1}{i_2} \left(\frac{Z_E Z_H Z_\epsilon Z_\beta}{[\sigma_H]} \right)^2}$$

(2) Parameter determination :

Load factor $K = K_A \cdot K_V \cdot K_\alpha \cdot K_\beta$

1. The use coefficient is obtained from Table 6-4 of the textbook $K_A = 1$;
2. Dynamic load coefficient, estimated circumferential velocity $v = 2 \text{m/s}$ at the index circle, $\frac{v \times z_1}{100} = 0.44$, obtained from Figure 6-11b[11] $K_A = 1.25$, $K_V = 1.06$
3. Inter-tooth load distribution coefficient K_α

As is known from Table 14-1-61[11], the degree of overlap of the end faces

$$\epsilon_a = \left[1.88 - 3.2 \left(\frac{1}{z_1} + \frac{1}{z_2} \right) \right] \cos \beta.$$

$$\epsilon_a = \left[1.88 - 3.2 \left(\frac{1}{30} + \frac{1}{30} \right) \right] \cos 10^\circ = 1.64.$$

Longitudinal coincidence

$$\epsilon_\beta = \frac{b \sin \beta}{\pi m_n} = \frac{\psi_d d \sin \beta}{\pi m_n} = \frac{\psi_d z_1 \tan \beta}{\pi m_n} = 1.23.$$

$$\epsilon_r = \epsilon_a + \epsilon_\beta = 1.64 + 1.23 = 2.87.$$

Obtained from Fig. 14-1-29c $K_\alpha = 1.42$

4. Tooth load distribution coefficient, due to $\psi_d = 1.0$.

Check Table 14-1-65[11] $K_\beta = 1.36$;

$$\text{Load factor } K = K_A \cdot K_V \cdot K_\alpha \cdot K_\beta = 1.25 \times 1.06 \times 1.2 \times 1.42 = 2.26,$$

5. known $T_2 = 0.46 \text{N.m}$

6. Node area coefficient $Z_H = 4.46$, ($\beta = 10^\circ$ obtained by checking Table 14-1-66);

7. elastic influence coefficient $Z_E = 489.8 \text{MPa}$

8. The coincidence coefficient, because, $\epsilon_\beta \geq 1$, then take, $\epsilon_\beta = 1$, so obtain

$$Z_\epsilon = \sqrt{\frac{4 + \epsilon_a}{3} (1 - \epsilon_\beta) + \frac{\epsilon_\beta}{\epsilon_a}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\epsilon_a}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{1.68}} = 0.77.$$

9. Helix angle coefficient $Z_\beta = \sqrt{\cos \beta} = \sqrt{\cos 10^\circ} = 0.99$.

10. Contact fatigue strength limit: $\sigma_{Hlim1} = 550\text{MPa}$, $\sigma_{Hlim2} = 450\text{MPa}$

11. Calculate the number of stress cycles:

$$N_1 = 60 \cdot n_2 \cdot j \cdot L = 60 \times 966.66 \times 1 \times (5 \times 300 \times 8) = 5.76 \times 10^8.$$

$$N_2 = \frac{N_1}{i_2} = \frac{5.76 \times 10^8}{3} = 1.92 \times 10^8.$$

12. Take $N = 5.76 \times 10^8$ the contact fatigue life coefficient.

$$K_{HN1} = 1.0, \quad K_{HN2} = 1.02$$

The failure rate is 1%, and the safety factor $S = 1$ is obtained

$$[\sigma_H]_1 = \frac{K_{HN1} \sigma_{Hlim1}}{S} = \frac{1.0 \times 550}{1} = 550\text{MPa}.$$

$$[\sigma_H]_2 = \frac{K_{HN2} \sigma_{Hlim2}}{S} = \frac{1.02 \times 450}{1} = 450\text{MPa}.$$

Take $[\sigma_H] = 450\text{MPa}$

13. Trial selection load coefficient $K_t = 1.6$

(3) Calculation :

(1) Pinion index circle diameter d_{3t}

$$d_{3t} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{2KT_2}{\psi_d} \cdot \frac{i_2 + 1}{i_2} \left(\frac{Z_E Z_H Z_\epsilon Z_\beta}{[\sigma_H]} \right)^2}$$

$$= \sqrt[3]{\frac{2 \times 2.26 \times 0.46 \times 10^3}{1} \cdot \frac{3+1}{3} \left(\frac{489.8 \times 4.46 \times 0.77 \times 0.992}{450} \right)^2} = 16\text{mm}$$

(2) Calculate the circumferential velocity at the average index circle

$$v_3 = \frac{\pi \cdot d_1 \cdot n_2}{60 \times 1000} = \frac{\pi \times 16 \times 966.67}{60 \times 1000} = 0.81\text{m/s}.$$

(3) Correction of load factor $\frac{v_3 \times z_1}{100} = \frac{0.81 \times 15}{100} = 0.12$.

(4) Correct the trial calculation of the big-end indexing circle diameter

$$d_3 = d_{3t} \cdot \sqrt[3]{\frac{K}{K_t}} = 35.26 \times \sqrt[3]{\frac{2.26}{1.6}} = 39.56\text{mm}.$$

(5) Calculate the normal modulus: $m_n = \frac{d_3 \cdot \cos \beta}{z_1} = \frac{39.56 \times \cos 10^\circ}{22} = 1.77$.

Due to the need for lubrication, the modulus is standardized to $m = 2$.

(6) Calculate the center distance $a = \frac{(z_1 + z_2)m_n}{2 \cos \beta} = \frac{(22 + 92) \times 2}{2 \cos 10^\circ} = 115.76 \approx 116$.

(7) Correct the helix angle according to the center distance after rounding

$$\beta = \arccos \left[\frac{(z_1 + z_2)m_n}{2a} \right] = 10.65^\circ.$$

(8) Calculate the index circle diameter

$$d_3 = \frac{z_3 m}{\cos \beta} = \frac{22 \times 2}{\cos 10.65^\circ} = 44.77\text{mm}.$$

$$d_4 = \frac{z_4 m}{\cos \beta} = \frac{66 \times 2}{\cos 10.65^\circ} = 134.31\text{mm}.$$

(9) Calculate the gear width $b_1 = \psi_d \cdot d_3 = 36.92\text{mm}$

Rounded to $b_1 = 45\text{mm}$, the width of the big gear teeth is usually smaller than the pinion so $b_2 = 40\text{mm}$

(4) Cylindrical gear transmission strength check

$$\sigma_{F3} = \frac{2 \cdot KT_2}{bd_3 m} Y_{Fa3} Y_{Sa3} Y_\varepsilon Y_\beta \leq [\sigma]_{F1}$$

$$\sigma_{F4} = \sigma_{F3} \frac{Y_{Fa4} Y_{Sa4}}{Y_{Fa3} Y_{Sa3}} \leq [\sigma]_{F2}$$

1. Coincidence coefficient $Y_\varepsilon = 0.25 + \frac{0.75}{\varepsilon_\alpha} = 0.25 + \frac{0.75}{1.67} = 0.70$ (Equation 6-11).

2. Helix angle coefficient $Y_\beta = 1 - \varepsilon_\beta \frac{\beta}{120^\circ} = 0.826$

3. Calculate the equivalent number of teeth $Z_{v3} = \frac{Z_3}{\cos^3 \beta} = 27.18$,

$$Z_{v4} = \frac{Z_4}{\cos^3 \beta} = 69.53.$$

4. Check the tooth shape coefficient

Retrieved from Figure 6-21 $Y_{Fa3} = 2.62$, $Y_{Fa4} = 2.18$,

Check the stress correction factor

Retrieved from Figure 6-22 $Y_{Sa3} = 1.58$, $Y_{Sa4} = 1.78$

5. Calculate bending fatigue, ultimate stress and life coefficient

$$\sigma_{F \text{ lim}3} = 420 \text{MPa} \quad (HB_1 = 240).$$

$$\sigma_{F \text{ lim}4} = 390 \text{MPa} \quad (HB_1 = 190).$$

6. Life factor

$$\text{Press } N_1 = 5.76 \times 10^8, \quad N_2 = 1.37 \times 10^8,$$

$$\text{Separately found } K_{FN3} = K_{FN4} = 1,$$

6. Calculate the allowable stress of bending fatigue, take the failure probability as 1%, and the safety factor S=1

$$[\sigma_{F3}] = K_{FN3} \sigma_{F \text{ lim}3} = 420 \text{MPa}.$$

$$[\sigma_{F4}] = K_{FN3} \sigma_{F \text{ lim}4} = 390 \text{MPa}.$$

7. Calculate bending stress

$$\sigma_{F3} = \frac{2 \cdot KT_2}{bd_3 m} Y_{Fa3} Y_{Sa3} Y_\varepsilon Y_\beta.$$

$$= \frac{2 \times 2.26 \times 0.46 \times 10^3}{45 \times 44.77 \times 2} \times 2.62 \times 1.58 \times 0.70 \times 0.826 = 1.23 \text{MPa}.$$

$$\sigma_{F3} \leq [\sigma_{F3}] = 420 \text{MPa}.$$

$$\sigma_{F4} = \sigma_{F3} \frac{Y_{Fa4} Y_{Sa4}}{Y_{Fa3} Y_{Sa3}} \leq [\sigma]_{F2}$$

$$= 1.23 \times \frac{2.18 \times 1.78}{2.62 \times 1.58} = 1.15 \text{MPa}.$$

$$\sigma_{F4} \leq [\sigma_{F4}] = 390 \text{MPa}.$$

By $\sigma_{F3} \leq [\sigma_{F3}]$, $\sigma_{F4} \leq [\sigma_{F4}]$ established, meet strength requirements

2. Design of axis two

(1) Selection of material: 45 high-quality carbon structural steel, quenched and tempered. Initial shaft diameter $P_1 = 47.43$ From table 9-8^[23] to get $C = 106 \sim 135$, we select $C = 120$

$$d_{min} = C \sqrt[3]{\frac{P_2}{n_2}} = 120 \times \sqrt[3]{\frac{47.43 \times 10^{-3}}{966.67}} = 4.39 \text{mm}.$$

It is known that cylindrical helical gears $z_1 = 22$, $z_2 = 92$, $m = 2$, $T_2 = 0.46 \text{N} \cdot \text{m}$

$$\alpha = 20^\circ \quad \beta = 10.65^\circ.$$

$$d_{m1} = d_1(1 - 0.5\psi_R) = 44.77 \times (1 - 0.5 \times 0.16) = 41.18\text{mm}.$$

3. Design of axis three

(1) **Selection of material:** 45 high-quality carbon structural steel, quenched and tempered.

(2). Structural design of the shaft

d_{1-2} : The design of shaft section 1-2, in order to meet the minimum diameter requirements, and query the coupling standard (GB/T5843-2003), take $d_{1-2} = 20\text{mm}$, $l_1 = 50\text{mm}$.

d_{2-3} : Design of shaft section 2-3, due to the needs of coupling shoulder positioning, take the diameter difference of the first two sections is 6 to 8mm, and because the second section shaft diameter needs to meet the J-type skeleton rubber oil seal (GB/T13871-1992) size standard, take $d_{2-3} = 24\text{mm}$; add this thickness of the gasket set to take $l_2 = 26\text{mm}$.

d_{3-4} , d_{7-8} : The design of the shaft section 3-4, 7-8, according to the proposed selection of the roller bearings, design the appropriate shaft diameter size and shaft section length. Take $d_{3-4} = 26\text{mm}$. The selected model is C107. Its main parameters are $d=26\text{mm}$, $D=52\text{mm}$, $B=14\text{mm}$. therefore $d_3 = d_4 = 26\text{mm}$. The left end bearing adopts shaft shoulder positioning, and the right end bearing is the sleeve positioning, so the length of the two shafts $l_3 = 14\text{mm}$, $l_7 = 14\text{mm}$

d_{5-6} : The design of the shaft section 5-6, the positioning scheme adopted at the left end of the large cylindrical gear is the shaft shoulder positioning, and the positioning scheme adopted at the right end is the sleeve positioning, which can be determined according to the above fixed shaft diameter $d_{5-6} = 30\text{mm}$, The width of the large gear teeth is $b = 30\text{mm}$ so it is desirable $l_5 = 30\text{mm}$.

d_{6-7} : Design of shaft segments 6-7, take $d_{6-7} = 26\text{mm}$, $l_6 = 14\text{mm}$. d_{4-5} : The design of the shaft section 4-5, the positioning scheme adopted by the right end face of the large cylindrical gear and the right end face of the left bearing are all shaft shoulder positioning $d_{4-5} = 32\text{mm}$, $l_4 = 30\text{mm}$

(3) Circumferential positioning of parts on the shaft

The circumferential positioning of gears, couplings and shafts are all connected with flat keys. In order to ensure that the gear and shaft have a good matching and neutrality, the matching between the gear hub and the shaft is selected $H7/n6$; The coupling is connected to the shaft and fits in $H7/r6$. The circumferential positioning of tapered roller bearings is ensured by a transition fit, and the diameter dimension tolerance of the selected shaft here is $K6$.

Tolerance annotation of each segment:

d_{1-2} : Cooperate with the coupling, take $\phi 20r6$

d_{3-4} , d_{7-8} : Fit with bearings, take $\phi 26K6$

d_{5-6} : Compatible with large cylindrical gear $\phi 28H7/m6$

(4) **The chamfer of the two shaft ends is $2 \times 45^\circ$.** According to the positioning of the gear shaft shoulder $r < C < a$, the fillet on the shaft is $R = 1\text{mm}$. It is not indicated that the rounded corner is $R = 0.5\text{mm}$, and the acute angle is blunt

(5) calculation of the support reaction force on the horizontal plane

Know condition $T_3 = 1.35\text{N}\cdot\text{m}$, $n_2 = \frac{322.22r}{\min}$, $d_3 = 187.22\text{mm}$, $\beta = 10.65^\circ$,

$$P = 45.05\text{W}.$$

Initial shaft diameter. From table 9-8 to get $C = 106 \sim 135$, we select $C = 108$

$$d_{min} = C \sqrt[3]{\frac{P_2}{n_2}} = 108 \times \sqrt[3]{\frac{45.05 \times 10^{-3}}{322.22}} = 5.60\text{mm}.$$

$$d_{m1} = d_1(1 - 0.5\psi_R) = 187.22 \times (1 - 0.5 \times 0.16) = 172.24\text{mm.}$$

$$\text{Tangential force: } F_{t3} = \frac{2T_3}{d_3} = \frac{2 \times 1.35 \times 10^3}{187.22} = 14.42\text{N}$$

$$\text{Radial force } F_{r3} = F_{t3} \frac{\tan\alpha_n}{\cos\beta} = 14.42 \times \frac{\tan 20^\circ}{\cos 10.65^\circ} = 5.34\text{N}$$

$$\text{The axial force } F_{a3} = F_{t3} \tan\beta = 14.42 \times \tan 10.65^\circ = 2.71\text{N}$$

$$\text{Thus } l_3 = 40\text{mm} \quad l_2 = 60\text{mm}$$

$$\text{Then } R_{1H} = \frac{F_{r3}l_2}{l_2+l_3} = 3.20\text{N} \quad R_{2H} = F_r - R_{1H} = 2.14\text{N}$$

$$\text{On the vertical plane } R_{1V} = \frac{F_t l_2}{l_2+l_3} = 8.65\text{N} \quad R_{2V} = F_t - R_{1V} = 11.22\text{N}$$

$$\text{The total support reaction on the bearing 1 } R_1 = \sqrt{R_{1H}^2 + R_{1V}^2} = 9.22\text{N}$$

$$\text{The total support reaction on the bearing 2 } R_2 = \sqrt{R_{2H}^2 + R_{2V}^2} = 11.42\text{N}$$

$$\text{Moment on the horizontal plane a-a } M_{aH} = R_{1H}l_3 = 128\text{N}\cdot\text{mm}$$

$$\text{On the vertical plane } M_{aV} = R_{1V}l_3 = 346\text{N}\cdot\text{mm}$$

The synthetic bending moment

$$\text{The a-a profile is } M_a = \sqrt{M_{aH}^2 + M_{aV}^2} = 368.91\text{N}\cdot\text{mm}$$

(5) check of axis three

Figure 3-4 Axis one and force analysis

Fatigue strength check of shaft:

Cross-section modulus \$Z\$ with flat keyway shaft, \$Z_p\$: check table 6-1-25^[22], \$Z = 0.65\$

$$Z_p = 1.4,$$

Mechanical properties of shaft: \$\sigma - 1 = 255\$ found by Table 6-1-1;

Medium carbon steel $\Psi_i = 0.1$;

The stress concentration coefficient K_σ at the fillet corner, K_r : check table 6-1-28,

$K_\sigma = 1.75, K_r = 1.4$,

The stress concentration coefficient K_σ at the keyway is obtained by looking at Table 6-1-30, $K_\sigma = 1.78, K_r = 1.54$;

Surface roughness coefficient KR : check table 6-1-32, $KR = 1.23$;

Absolute size influence coefficients ϵ_σ and ϵ_τ : check table 6-1-31 to obtain $\epsilon_\sigma = 0.77$,

$\epsilon_\tau = 0.75$.

obtained by the $\lambda_\sigma = \frac{K_\sigma + KR + 1}{\epsilon_\sigma}$, $\lambda_r = \frac{K_r + KR - 1}{\epsilon_r}$ formula

Fillet = 2.9, keyway= λ_σ 2.4 , fit $\lambda_\sigma = 2.2$ (found in Table 6-1-27). λ_σ

Fillet = 2.1, keyway= λ_r 2.2, mating = 1.7 λ_r (found in Table 6-1-27). λ_r

It is obtained by the formula $S = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{\lambda_\sigma M}{z}\right)^2 + 0.75 \cdot \left[\left(\lambda_\sigma + \varphi r\right) \frac{T}{z p}\right]^2}}$

$\lambda_\sigma, \lambda_r$ both take the greater value. $S = 2.9$, greater than the allowable safety factor

$[S] = 1.8$. Therefore, the fatigue strength of the shaft is sufficient. Since the load of the shaft is small, the static strength

of the shaft is sufficient. $\sigma_{F4} = \sigma_{F3} \frac{Y_{Fa4} Y_{Sa4}}{Y_{Fa3} Y_{Sa3}}$.

Circuit design

The robot is equipped with advanced sensors and cameras, including a lidar sensor which allow it to capture detailed data and images to identify potential issues or areas of concern. the autonomous navigation of the robot is realised by using SLAM (simultaneous localization and Mapping) and LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) technology with the help of ROS (Robot Operating System), the robot can conduct inspection without any human intervention, increasing efficiency and reducing safety risks.

The hardware structure of the robot includes a master computer deploys the model and analyses the comprehensive data, while the slave computer is utilized to directly control the external circuit, as shown in the figure. Information sharing between them is done using serial communication. The master computer is the raspberry pi control board. The

Table 4-1 Motion and dynamic

slave computer is an Arduino-uno control board, which controls the base of a car, collects pertinent information from sensors responsible for motion control.

Hardware Component :Here is a short list of different components that will allows the robot the perform the task assigned to it and perform according to the desired goal.

Raspberry pi

Micro-controller

Lidar

Depth camera D435

Battery

L928N

MQ-7 sensor

TMP36

IMU

Design Architecture

Main feature of the circuit

This circuit will allow to robot to:

- Navigate Autonomously in the indoor environment
- Use lidar and SLAM to generate a map of a room and navigate autonomously
- Use a camera with OpenCV to detect objects.

Application

Differential drive control (using ros2_control)^[24];

Mappin and localization with SLAM (using Slam_toolbox)^[25, 26];

Autonomous navigation (using Nav2)^[27];

Detecting an object with the camera (using Opencv).

L298N motor driver

L298N is a dedicated driver IC and belongs to the H-bridge IC. The IC can increase the output current and increase the power. The output current of the L298N dedicated driver IC is 2A, and its maximum current can reach 4A. The maximum operating voltage is 50V. The L298N dedicated drive IC can drive DC motors, stepper motors and other inductive loads. When the output of the L298N dedicated drive integrated circuit is connected to a single-chip microcomputer, it is convenient to control the output of the circuit through the single-chip microcomputer, so as to control the speed, steering and start-stop functions of the motor connected to it.

Figure 4-1 Motor driver chip L298N

Figure 4-2 L298N pin distribution

The figure below shows the internal schematic of the L298N.

Figure 4-3 L298N internal schematic

Figure 4-4 L298N drive motor circuit diagram

L298N Motor Controller Truth Table			
ENA	IN1	IN2	Description
0	N/A	N/A	Motor A is off
1	0	0	Motor A is stopped (brakes)
1	0	1	Motor A is on and turning backwards
1	1	0	Motor A is on and turning forwards
1	1	1	Motor A is stopped (brakes)

Table 4-2 L298N logic function table

The INA1 and INA2 pins of the L298N control the steering of the motor, PWM1 is the power supply enabler, and PWM is used to control the rms value of the output voltage, that is, to control the motor speed.

The circuit diagram principle of L298N drive motor is as follows:

Under the premise of PWM1=1.

If INA1=1, INA2=0, OUTA1=VS, OUTA2=0, then a relative potential difference is generated at both ends of the motor, resulting in rotation (assuming forward rotation).

If INA1=0, INA2=1, OUTA1=0, OUTA2=VS, the relative potential difference between the two ends of the motor occurs, resulting in rotation (compared with the previous input, at this time it is reversed).

If INA1=0, INA2=0, OUTA1=0, OUTA2=0, both ends of the motor are zero, there is no relative potential difference, cannot rotate.

If INA1=1, INA2=1, OUTA1=VS, OUTA2=VS, both ends of the motor generate forward voltage, but there is no relative potential difference between them, and it cannot rotate;

At PWM1=0, all outputs are zero and the motor cannot rotate.

Such a piece of L298N can just control the start-stop and speed of the two motors, the light intensity signal collected by the photoelectric sensor, and then through the comparator and reverser of the detection circuit module, the optical signal is converted into a digital signal, and the digital signal is transmitted to the single-chip microcomputer, and then the control program logic judges the received signal control drive circuit to control the speed and start and stop of the motor.

The Arduino microcontroller^[28] is based on the Atmel AVR microcontroller, and is programmed using the Arduino integrated development environment (IDE), which is based on the Processing programming language. The IDE allows users to write, compile, and upload code to the Arduino board, and includes a library of pre-written code that can be used to easily interface with a variety of sensors, motors, and other components.

Figure 4-4 Arduino Uno Microcontroller

Table 4-3 Connection of the LN928 motor driver to Arduino

+12V	5 – 35 V power supply
GND	Power supply and Arduino ground
IN1	Pin 6 Arduino
IN2	Pin 7 Arduino
IN3	Pin 5 Arduino
IN4	Pin 4 Arduino
ENA and ENB jumper	Leave installed
OUT1 + OUT2	Stepper motor coil A
OUT3 + OUT4	Stepper motor coil B

The figure below shows the connection diagram of Arduino Uno and the L928N.

Figure 4-5 L928N connected to Arduino Uno diagram

Figure 4-6 Fritzing diagram of L928N and Arduino Uno

Raspberry pi

The microprocessor Raspberry pi 4^[29] is the brain of the robot. Raspberry Pi is a powerful computing platform that can handle complex algorithms and machine learning models needed for autonomous navigation. It is built with ethernet, Wi-Fi, and Bluetooth connectivity, which allows it to communicate with other devices and sensors and it can run a variety of operating system. We will need to install Ubuntu software on and it will run ROS for the Robot control. To run ROS easily, we want our OS to be Ubuntu Linux. This series will be using the Foxy version ROS 2 which means it needs Ubuntu 20.04 Focal to be compatible. Then we upload our Ros packages on the Raspberry pi. And ALL this stuff is connected to the brains of this operation, a Raspberry Pi, running Linux and ROS.

Figure 4-7 Raspberry Pi 4B

CPU	Broadcom BCM2711, quad-core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit SoC @ 1.5GHz
RAM	8GB
Connectivity	2.4 GHz and 5.0 GHz IEEE 802.11b/g/n/ac wireless LAN, Bluetooth 5.0, BLE Gigabit Ethernet 2 × USB 3.0 ports 2 × USB 2.0 ports
Input Power	5V/3A

Table 4-4 Raspberry Pi specifications

Connecting an Arduino to a Raspberry Pi via USB is a simple and effective way to communicate between the two devices. It allows for the use of the powerful processing capabilities of the Raspberry Pi with the ability to interface with a wide range of sensors and other electronic components using the Arduino.

Figure 4-8 Raspberry Pi 4B connected to Arduino

A regulator might be needed to convert the input power to an adjustable power needed for the raspberry pi and Arduino, the DFR205 is suitable.

Figure 4-9 Fritzing wiring diagram of Raspberry Pi 4B connected to Arduino

Mapping and Localisation

Mapping: The robot can identify the environment by a mapping process using Lidar technology. Lidar stands for **Light Detection and Ranging** is a remote sensing technology that uses laser light to measure distances to objects and create a 3D map of the surrounding environment. LiDAR works by emitting laser pulses that bounce off objects in the environment and return to the sensor. The sensor measures the time it takes for the pulses to return and uses this information to calculate the distance to each object. LiDAR sensors can be classified into two types: scanning and non-scanning. Scanning which are categorised in three main categories, which are the one Dimension, 2D and 3D.

Figure 4-10 Different types of Lidar

We choose to use a 2D lidar sensor. 2D lidar works by emitting a laser beam and measuring the time it takes for the beam to bounce back after hitting an object. By rotating the sensor, it can capture a 360-degree view of its surroundings and create a 2D map that represents the distances of the objects in the environment

Figure 4-11 Lidar connection to Raspberry Pi

Lidar Pin	Raspberry Pi Pin	Colour	Min	Typical	Max
Pin 1 (TX)	Pin 10 (RXD)	White	0V	3.3V	3.5V
Pin 2 (PWM)	Pin 12 (PWMO)	Yellow	-	-	3.3V
Pin 3 (GND)	Pin 6 (GND)	Red	0V	0V	-
Pin 4 (P5V)	Pin 4 (5V)	Blue	5V	5V	5.5V

Table 4-5 Lidar wire connection to Raspberry Pi

localization: The position of the robot can be known by the use of SLAM. SLAM stands for Simultaneous Localization and Mapping; it is a technique used in robotics to build a map of an unknown environment while simultaneously maintaining track of the robot's position within that environment. SLAM enables robots to understand and interact with their surroundings in real-time, allowing the robot to navigate autonomously.

The SLAM algorithm works by analysing data collected from sensors, such as cameras, LiDAR, and wheel encoders. The algorithm uses this data to create a map of the environment, while also estimating the robot's position within the map. The SLAM algorithm operates in a loop, with the robot continuously updating its position and map as it moves through the environment. The SLAM and LiDAR technologies work together to create a comprehensive picture of the

robot's surroundings. LiDAR provides a 3D map of the environment, while SLAM algorithms build a map of the environment while simultaneously tracking the robot's position within the environment

Figure 4-12 Lidar generated map

Navigation: The Robot use ROS package to navigate through its environment. The navigation stack in ROS provides a set of pre-built software packages that make it easier to set up and run a navigation system on a robot. These packages include the AMCL (Adaptive Monte Carlo Localization) algorithm for localization, the move base package for path planning and motion control, and the map server package for handling maps. To use the navigation stack in ROS, the robot needs to have a sensor suite that includes a 2D or 3D lidar, wheel encoders, and an IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) for odometry. The sensor data is then processed through the SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) algorithm to generate a map of the environment, which the robot can use for localization and path planning. Once the robot has a map of the environment, the AMCL algorithm is used to localize the robot within the map using sensor data. The move base package then takes in a target destination and generates a path to the goal, while avoiding obstacles detected by the lidar. The motion controller then uses the path to generate motor commands to move the robot towards the goal.

Odometry: Odometry sensors are used to track the movement of the robot and calculate its position based on the distance and direction of its wheel rotations. an odometry sensor consists of an encoder that is attached to the motor of the robot's wheel. The encoder measures the rotation of the wheel and sends this information to the robot's control system. By analysing the rotation data from both wheels, the control system can estimate the position and orientation of the robot.

Wheel encoder tick data to the digital signals sent by the wheel encoders of a mobile robot to indicate the distance travelled by each wheel. Each time a wheel completes a full rotation, the encoder generates a specific number of ticks, which corresponds to a certain distance travelled by the wheel. These encoders provide feedback to the robot's control system regarding the distance travelled by each wheel, which can be used to estimate the robot's position and velocity. IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) is a sensor used in mobile robots to measure the linear and angular motion of the robot. It consists of a combination of accelerometers and gyroscopes that provide information on the robot's velocity, position, and orientation. IMU connection to raspberry pi.

Figure 4-14 IMU connected to Raspberry Pi

Planning algorithm: Indoor robot navigation refers to the process of robot moving from the starting point to the target point. The robot locates itself using the saved map and lidar during this time, and then plans the best course based on its own location and predetermined destination point. Finally, the robot generally follows this course to go to the target place. Depending on the scale of the action, path planning is classified into global planning and local planning.

Figure 4-14 Path planning algorithm chart flow

Working with ROS: ROS (Robot Operating System) is an open-source middleware framework used in robotics for building and controlling robot applications. It provides a set of tools, libraries, and conventions that allow developers to create complex robot applications by abstracting low-level hardware details and providing a unified communication system. One of the key features of ROS is its communication system, which allows different nodes (modules) in a robot system to exchange information with each other.

ROS code and node will control the displacement of the robot throughout the indoor environment. Working on a project with ROS, we keep all our code and files and stuff in something called a package. And a package is basically just a normal folder with a couple of special files in it so ROS knows what to do.

Figure 4-15 ROS package

Differential drive control in ROS

ROS has a special function call ROS REPS. This REP specifies naming conventions and semantic meaning for coordinate frames of mobile platforms used with ROS. The coordinate frame called `base_link` is rigidly attached to the mobile robot base in any arbitrary position or orientation; for every hardware platform there will be a different place on the base that provides an obvious point of reference. The coordinate frame called `odom` is a world-fixed frame. The coordinate frame called `map` is a world fixed frame, with its Z-axis pointing upwards.

Relation between frames:

The main thing that controls the displacement of the robot is the velocity. The control system will do is take a command velocity input, translated into motor commands for the motor drivers, read the actual motor speeds back out, and calculate the true velocity.

With ROS, that command velocity is on a topic called /cmd_vel, and the type is /Twist, which is just six numbers - linear velocity in the x y and z axes, and angular velocity around each axis. For a differential drive robot though, we can only control two things: linear speed in x (driving forward and backwards), and angular speed in z (turning), so the other four numbers will always be 0.

The image below shows how the nodes named Knex-ros works. The purpose of this package is to provide an interface to the navigation stack. It takes in a twist message from the navigation stack, and provides a left wheel and right wheel

messages to be used as motor driver strengths. The package receives wheel encoder messages back from the hardware

Figure 4-16 Differential drive package

and generates the tf transform messages required by the ROS navigation stack. This package provides the following nodes:

- Diff_tf - Provides the base_link transform.
- Pid_velocity - A basic PID controller with a velocity target.
- Twist_to_motors - Translates a twist to two motor velocity targets

Experimental analysis

To simulate the robot, we use Gazebo software. Gazebo is an open-source 3D robotics simulator that provides a realistic and physics-based environment for simulating robots. It allows users to create virtual worlds and models, simulate robot behaviours, and test algorithms before deploying them on physical robots. Gazebo offers features such as physics simulation, sensor modelling, 3D visualization, and integration with ROS, making it a valuable tool for robot development and testing. Its capabilities make it an essential tool for robot developers, researchers, and hobbyists, providing a cost-effective and efficient way to test and validate robotic systems in a virtual environment before deploying them in the real world.

Simulation process

To create a simulation of a mobile robot using ROS (Robot Operating System) and Gazebo, we followed these general steps

1. Set up ROS and Gazebo: Install ROS on your system by following the official ROS installation instructions. Gazebo is commonly bundled with ROS, so it should be installed automatically. Make sure both ROS and Gazebo are properly configured and working on your system.
2. Create a ROS package: Use the 'catkin_create_pkg' command to create a new ROS package. This package will contain all the necessary files for your simulation.
3. Design the robot model: Define the robot's physical characteristics and geometry by creating a Unified Robot Description Format (URDF) file. This XML-based file describes the robot's links, joints, sensors, and other properties. Specify the visual and collision properties of the robot's components in the URDF.
4. Add sensors and actuators: If your robot has sensors such as cameras, LiDAR, or IMUs, include them in the URDF file. Specify the sensor properties and their relative positions with respect to the robot's frame of reference. Additionally, if your robot has actuators like motors or servos, define them in the URDF as well.
5. Create a world file: Define the simulated environment where your robot will operate by creating a Gazebo world file. This file describes the physical properties of the environment, such as the ground, objects, lighting, and other elements. You can also specify dynamic elements like moving obstacles or dynamic lighting effects.
6. Integrate ROS and Gazebo: Create launch files that combine the robot model, sensor configuration, and Gazebo world. Launch files are XML files that specify the nodes and parameters to be run. They enable you to start Gazebo with your robot model and load the necessary ROS nodes and configurations.
7. Test and iterate: Launch the simulation and observe the behaviour of your robot in the simulated environment. Use ROS tools and commands to visualize sensor data, control the robot, and interact with the simulation. If needed, adjust the URDF, world file, or other components based on your desired simulation behaviour.

8. Implement robot control: Develop ROS nodes that control your simulated robot. These nodes can subscribe to sensor data, perform perception or mapping tasks, and send control commands to the simulated robot. Implement algorithms for navigation, path planning, or any other specific behaviour you want to simulate.
9. Debug and refine: Test and debug your simulation by running various scenarios and verifying the behaviour of your robot. Refine the simulation by iterating on the design, control algorithms, or environment until you achieve the desired results

Stereo mapping: Stereo mapping algorithms are used to calculate the depth of each point generated from the ray casting algorithm. By using the generated stereo calibration parameters, ray casted points are projected on to the other stereo camera image plane as epipolar lines. In rectified image plane, epipolar lines become parallel horizontal lines. Therefore, stereo correspondence process becomes faster and efficient as the search can be done along the rows of the image. The corresponding point can be searched in the second image by detecting the locations where the laser beam cuts each epipolar line, which can be easily done by searching for highest intensity value. Usually, two intersection points are detected due to the circular shape of the laser beam. Hence, in order to identify the correct match, the search algorithm can be updated to classify the points according to their location with respect to the center. Equations (5), (6) and (7) represent the high level calculations of the stereo mapping functionality.

When the disparity value taken as d , camera focal length defined as f , distance between two camera focal points defined as T , coordinates of the object position defined as $P=(X_p, Y_p, Z_p)$, object coordinates in the left camera image defined as $pl=(x_l, y_l)$ and object coordinates in the right camera image defined as $pr=(x_r, y_r)$; the relation between the coordinates can be defined as below;

$$d = (x_l - x_r) \quad (5)$$

$$x_l = \frac{X_p f}{Z_p}; \quad x_r = \frac{(X_p - T)f}{Z_p}; \quad y_l = y_r = \frac{Y_p f}{Z_p}; \quad (6)$$

From (5) and (6):

$$Z_p = f \frac{T}{x_l - x_r} = f \frac{T}{d}; \quad X_p = x_l \frac{T}{d}; \quad Y_p = y_l \frac{T}{d} \quad (7)$$

Once the depth information is available from the stereo mapping algorithm, it can be used to determine the orientation of the robot. If the robot tilt while moving forward the orientations are displayed on the system to manoeuvre it properly. An example depth calculation on two identified points is shown in Fig. 5.1. The depth information further can be used to show the pipe orientation in world coordinates. which is planned as a future enhancement.[12]

Figure 5-1 Feature depth calculation for camera tilt detection[12]

Gazebo robot differential control: Gazebo provides a differential drive plugin that enables the simulation of robots with a differential drive configuration. Gazebo's differential drive plugin provides simulation capabilities for robots with a differential drive configuration. This widely used drive system involves independently controlling two wheels. By accepting input commands for linear and angular velocities, the plugin allows precise control over the robot's forward and rotational movements. The integration with Gazebo's physics engine enables the application of realistic forces and torques to the wheels, replicating the motor control and motion of an actual robot. Moreover, the plugin offers odometry information based on wheel encoder readings, supporting localization and mapping functionalities. The seamless integration between Gazebo's differential drive plugin and ROS brings powerful capabilities to robot development and testing. Leveraging ROS commands, the plugin enables control of the robot and publishing of odometry data to ROS topics. This integration empowers developers to utilize ROS tools and libraries for the creation and evaluation of control algorithms and navigation systems. With customizable parameters such as wheel separation distance, wheel radius, and maximum wheel torque, the simulation can be tailored to accurately reflect the characteristics of the physical robot and its actuators. Through this comprehensive simulation environment, developers can refine their control strategies, test navigation approaches, and conduct various experiments before deploying them onto a physical robot, while taking advantage of ROS's extensive robotics ecosystem.

Figure 5-2 Robot navigation test[13]

Creating a 3D environment in Gazebo: To incorporate a 3D environment, such as a small house, into Gazebo, you need to follow a few steps. First, create or obtain a 3D model of the small house using software like Blender or SketchUp. Ensure the model is in a compatible format, such as Collada or Object. Next, modify the URDF file of your robot or create a separate URDF file specifically for the house model. Within the URDF file, define the visual and collision properties of the house, including the file path to the 3D model, position, orientation, scale, and any additional details like material properties. Once the URDF is set up, create or modify a Gazebo launch file to include the pipeline model. In the launch file, load the URDF file of the pipeline and set the necessary parameters, such as the initial pose of the pipeline within the Gazebo world. Launch the Gazebo simulation using the modified launch file, and the pipeline will be integrated into the simulation environment. By adding a 3D environment like a pipeline to Gazebo, we created a more realistic and immersive simulation for your robot. This allowed us to test and evaluate the robot's behaviour and interactions within a complex and visually appealing environment. It also provides an opportunity to develop and refine algorithms related to navigation, object detection, or path planning, considering the presence of obstacles and structures like the pipeline. By accurately modelling the environment, we gained valuable insights into the robot's performance and optimize its capabilities before deploying it in real-world scenarios.

Economic analysis

In order to design the system to be economically feasible, the costs of the system should outweigh the costs of conventional above ground leak detection. Apart from that, a certain added value might be attributed to the system due to:

- Detection of more, and possibly smaller leaks
- More accurate positional data of leaks (centimeter accuracy instead of meter).
- Data about position, orientation, material and quality of the pipe
- Preventive indication of risk areas due to corrosion and deformation.

In the economic discussion of the system, the following aspects are important for design of the system:

- System costs: the system itself, equipment, personnel, maintenance and development
- The amount of data yielded by the system (try to attribute an economic value to the detection of the location of a leak, depending on the accuracy of this data, the public risk in the searched area)
- The speed with which data can be acquired from a given (subset) of the gas distribution network
- Life span and life cycle of the system.

We will use a 3D printer to print the robot chassis. Carbon fibre material are chosen to print the robot chassis. Carbon fibre is a lightweight and strong material that is commonly used in aerospace and automotive industries. It has excellent tensile strength and is highly resistant to impact, making it a good choice for high-performance mobile robot chassis. The life expectancy of carbon fiber depends on several factors, including its quality, usage conditions, and maintenance. Generally, high-quality carbon fiber materials can last for up to 25 years or more with proper care and maintenance. It is relatively expensive compared to other materials. Generally, carbon fiber filaments for 3D printing can range from \$40 to \$150 per kilogram, with some high-end materials costing up to \$500 per kilogram. The Arduino uno and raspberry have a live expectancy of 3 to 5 years. The cost of an Arduino Uno board is relatively low and can be purchased for around \$20-\$30 USD. The life expectancy of an Arduino Uno depends on its usage and handling, but it is typically expected to last for several years. The cost of a Raspberry Pi board varies depending on the model and configuration, but can range from \$35 USD to over \$100 USD. The life expectancy of a Raspberry Pi also depends on its usage and handling, but it is generally expected to last for several years. 2D Lidar slamdec the price of the Slamtec RPLidar 2D can vary depending on the specific model and seller, but it generally ranges from around \$100 to \$500 USD. In terms of life

expectancy, the manufacturer claims that the Slamtec RPLidar 2D has a Mean Time Between Failure (MTBF) of over 20,000 hours, which is quite high. Camera Depth Camera D435 is a popular depth sensor used in many robotics applications. As for its cost, it currently ranges from around \$150 to \$200 USD. In terms of life expectancy, Intel RealSense provides a limited warranty of one year from the date of purchase for the D435 camera. Battery A high-quality 3000mAh LiFePO4 battery can cost between \$20 to \$50 or more. LiFePO4 batteries are known for their longer life expectancy compared to other lithium-ion batteries. A well-maintained LiFePO4 battery can last up to 10 years or more. Taking in account the motor driver, motor, wheel, and all other different sensor this whole project will cost around 500\$ with a life expectancy of over one year. This will definitely provide a high return on investment over the years to the industry. Despite the high initial and maintenance costs, inspection robots can provide significant benefits that can offset these costs. One of the main benefits of inspection robots is improved safety. Robots can be used to inspect hazardous or hard-to-reach areas, reducing the risk of injury to personnel. Additionally, robots can be equipped with sensors that can detect dangerous gases, temperature fluctuations, and other hazards, allowing for early detection and prevention of potential accidents.

The Inspection Robots Market is propelled by dynamic factors that underscore the industry's growth and evolution. One key driver is the increasing demand for automation in various sectors, including manufacturing, oil and gas, and utilities. Inspection robots play a pivotal role in enhancing efficiency and safety by conducting inspections in hazardous or hard-to-reach environments. The relentless pursuit of operational excellence and the need to minimize human intervention in high-risk areas drive the adoption of inspection robots across industries. Furthermore, advancements in sensor technologies and artificial intelligence contribute to the market dynamics, enabling these robots to provide more accurate and real-time data, ultimately improving decision-making processes for businesses.[14]

On the flip side, the Inspection Robots Market faces challenges related to high initial costs and the complexity of integrating robotic systems into existing workflows. Despite the long-term benefits, some industries may be hesitant to invest due to the significant upfront expenses associated with implementing inspection robots. Additionally, concerns about data security and privacy may act as a restraint, particularly in industries dealing with sensitive information. However, as technological advancements continue and the awareness of the long-term benefits grows, these challenges are expected to be mitigated, further fostering the market's growth.[14]

According to a report by Marketsand Markets, the global market for inspection robots is expected to grow from \$2.7 billion in 2020 to \$4.3 billion by 2025, representing a compound annual growth rate of 9.3%. This growth is driven by a number of factors, including increasing demand for automation and robotics in various industries, as well as improvements in the technology used in inspection robots. However, the field of robotics and inspection robots has witnessed significant investments globally. Several leading countries have allocated substantial funding to advance research, development, and deployment of inspection robots in various industries. The United States has been a major contributor to robotics investment, with significant funding from both public and private sectors. The U.S. government has supported robotics research and development through initiatives such as the National Robotics Initiative and funding agencies like DARPA (Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency). Additionally, private companies and venture capital firms in the U.S. have invested heavily in robotics technology, including inspection robots, as part of their innovation strategies. China has also made substantial investments in robotics and automation, including inspection robots. The Chinese government has identified robotics as a strategic area for development and has introduced various initiatives and funding programs to promote research, manufacturing, and deployment of robotic systems across different sectors. Chinese companies and research institutions have actively pursued advancements in inspection robot technology, particularly in industries such as manufacturing, logistics, and infrastructure. Germany, known for its strong manufacturing sector, has been investing in robotics and automation to enhance industrial processes and maintain competitiveness. The German government has supported research and development projects in robotics and offers funding opportunities through programs such as the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and

Energy's "Autonomics for Industry 4.0" initiative. German companies have also invested in inspection robots to improve quality control and optimize manufacturing operations. While these countries have seen significant investments, it's important to note that there are other countries around the world actively investing in inspection robot technologies. South Korea, Japan, and various European countries have also made notable investments in robotics and automation, including inspection robots, to drive innovation and address industry-specific challenges.

In recent years, China has made significant investments in the development and deployment of inspection robots in various industries, including manufacturing, construction, and healthcare. For example, in 2020, Chinese e-commerce giant JD.com announced that it would invest RMB 1 billion (\$150 million)^[31] in developing and deploying autonomous delivery robots and drones. In the healthcare sector, Chinese robotics company TMiRob received \$82 million in Series B funding in 2020 for its medical inspection robot, which can assist with tasks such as disinfection and patient monitoring. The United States has also seen significant investment in inspection robots, particularly in the manufacturing and defense industries. For example, in 2019, the U.S. Department of Defense awarded a \$13.5 million contract to robotics company Endeavor Robotics for the development of unmanned ground vehicles for explosive ordnance disposal. In the manufacturing sector, companies such as ABB Robotics and KUKA Robotics have developed inspection robots for tasks such as quality control and defect detection. Germany is known for its advanced manufacturing industry, and inspection robots have played a significant role in improving efficiency and productivity in this sector. For example, in 2020, German robotics company Franka Emika received €20 million (\$24 million) in Series A funding for its collaborative robots, which can be used for tasks such as assembly and inspection. Additionally, German automotive manufacturer BMW has deployed inspection robots in its factories to assist with tasks such as paint inspection and defect detection.

The Pipe Inspection Robot Market size is estimated to surpass USD 5 Billion by the end of 2036, witnessing around 15% during the forecast period, i.e., 2024 - 2036. In the year 2023, the industry size of pipe inspection robot was around USD 3 Billion. The growth of the market

Figure 6-1 Global market analysis of pipeline inspection robot

can be attributed to the growing network of gas pipelines. As of December 2020, there were around 2,381 operating oil and gas pipelines spread over 162 nations. Moreover, between 2022 and 2026, around 536 transmission oil and gas pipelines are expected to come online. With the expansion of pipelines, safety has become the paramount concern, pipe inspection robots provide a safe way of inspection.

In addition to these, a factor that is believed to fuel the market growth of pipe inspection robots is surging industrial growth. The necessity for constructing and extending infrastructure, such as pipelines for transversing fluids has increased dramatically with the expansion of the industrial sector. The higher the size and scope of an industrial

infrastructure, there's more the requirement for routine inspection and maintenance, which increases the demand for pipe inspection robots.[15]

Growth Drivers

- **Growing Improvement in the Structure** - There has been ongoing technological advancement in the structure of pipe inspection robots, such as the flexibility has been improved. Moreover, pipe inspections can reach longer distances owing to their improved signal transmission capability. Modern improvements in inspection robots have improved their navigation properties even in complex conditions. They can inspect different pipes of different diameters and negotiate bends.[15]
- **Rising Shift Towards Nanotechnology**- Cameras, sensors, and essential components used in pipe inspection robots can now be miniaturized by nanotechnology. Nanotechnology allows for the lowering of atomic dimensions and tolerances to less than 100nm, as well as the reduction of product size without compromising performance. Smaller structures will allow robots to navigate through smaller diameters.[15]
- **Rising Use of Drones for Surveillance**- Inspection drones mounted with night vision cameras and thermal imaging sensors can offer 24-hour observation, even in low-light or adverse conditions. Drones integrated with cameras and sensors help in providing the aerial view and they are suitable for identifying initial damages through aerial views.[15]

Challenges

The Rising Complexity of Pipeline Networks- Pipeline networks can be quite complicated, with a wide range of sizes, dimensions, and topologies. Creating inspection robots that can traverse different environments can be difficult.

- **Low Competency with the Existing Systems.**
- **Lack of Service Training and Expertise.**[15]

Furthermore, advancements in robotics technology, including improvements in sensor capabilities, artificial intelligence, and machine learning algorithms, have expanded the capabilities of inspection robots. This has allowed them to perform complex tasks, adapt to dynamic environments, and provide real-time data analysis and reporting. As these technologies continue to evolve, the market for inspection robots is expected to witness further growth and innovation. The market growth is also influenced by government initiatives, regulations, and safety standards that emphasize the use of automation and robotics in inspection processes. Governments around the world are increasingly recognizing the benefits of inspection robots in terms of safety, cost savings, and improved efficiency. As a result, they are encouraging the adoption of inspection robots through funding programs, tax incentives, and regulatory support. In addition, the market is driven by the growing focus on preventive maintenance and asset management in industries. Inspection robots play a crucial role in proactive maintenance strategies by enabling regular and thorough inspections, detecting potential issues early, and minimizing downtime. This helps companies optimize their operations, reduce maintenance costs, and extend the lifespan of their assets.

Overall, the market for inspection robots is projected to continue growing at a significant rate in the coming years. Industry reports and market research studies forecast a strong compound annual growth rate (CAGR) for the inspection robot market, driven by the increasing adoption of automation, advancements in robotics technology, and the ongoing need for efficient and reliable inspection solutions across industries.

Environmental Analysis

Inner pipeline inspection robot makes the inspection easier. Different types of IPIR are used for different scenarios and environments.

Robots Improve Recycling Processes: Automating waste treatment and recycling has shown to reduce CO₂ emissions as more materials are captured and able to be reused. Sorting robots use AI technology to scan, identify, and sort items that can be recycled. Prior to sorting robots, the process of recycling was done manually by workers. However, the manual sorting of waste was plagued by inefficiencies. Workers were not able to keep up with conveyors moving thousands of items and had a difficult time recognizing recyclable materials. Sorting robots are able to operate at fast speeds while their AI technology can quickly scan several items and alert them for recyclables. The FANUC M20ia can sort through hundreds of items within minutes. All recyclable items are identified, preventing them from being missed and kept as waste. Automating recycling processes with robots reduces pollution since more items are recycled and reused. [16]

Robots Reduce Material Waste: Not only can robots be utilized for sorting through waste, but they can also help prevent it in the first place. Industrial robots are designed to perform tasks with incredible precision and accuracy, using programming, robotic vision systems, and force sensors. Most material waste from manufacturing is the result of human error. Automating manufacturing processes with robots eliminates or greatly reduces the need for human interaction, which prevents errors from occurring. Articulated robots' area able to conserve raw materials, only using what is necessary and performing tasks correctly. This prevents materials and items from having to be discarded and turned into waste.

In the automotive industry, a FANUC M710ic/20L is used to cut sheet metal with a laser. It is programmed with the exact parameters to follow for every cycle turn, ensuring accurate cuts. If automated laser cutting were to be done manually, the chance of error increases along with the likelihood of increased waste. Automating with industrial robots cuts down on material waste, allowing for the efficient use of raw materials, helping to keep the environment clean.

Robots Reduce Energy Consumption: One of the main benefits of automating with industrial robots is that they optimize manufacturing. One of the advantages of optimized manufacturing is reduced energy consumption. Six axis robots are much faster and efficient than workers. One robot can complete the same workload that would require two to four workers. This means products are manufactured in less time with fewer resources being utilized, cutting down on energy use. In addition, robots can tolerate conditions what humans cannot such as dim lighting or hot or cold temperatures. Reducing the use of factory utilities conserves the amount of electricity consumed during manufacturing. Many of today's robots are also built with energy conserving features such as AC servo motors instead of DC servo motors. The FANUC M710ic/50 can help manufacturers concerned about their environmental footprint with its energy efficient features.[16]

Conclusion

This design of a four-wheel robot allows the robot to navigate autonomously, detect a change in temperature, identify toxic gases, and identify personal in order to ensure the safety of an inner side of the pipeline.

In terms of mechanical design, by calculating the weight of the robot, the size of the chassis is designed, and the required power is calculated according to the load, running speed and other data, so as to select the appropriate motor. The design of this mechanical part focuses on the design of the reducer, and through consulting the manual, using materials, strengthening the ability to design and check the shaft, calculate gear parameters, etc., so that I can more deeply integrate the knowledge I have learned into practice.

In the design of the electrical part, the corresponding scheme is first designed according to the predetermined function to be completed, and the corresponding scheme is designed by analyzing the method of the function to be completed. In this design, we want to realize the function of autonomous navigation where the robot will move without a human

intervention patrolling around the indoor environment while collecting data related to the safety of the facility, to achieve this task we selected the Lidar (Light Detection and Ranging) sensor technology that plays a crucial role in providing accurate and reliable data for autonomous navigation, enabling robots and vehicles to perceive their surroundings and make informed decisions and other sensors plus a camera. In the design we use two microcontroller the Raspberry Pi and an Arduino uno. The combination of a Raspberry Pi as the central processing unit and an Arduino to control the motor driver is a popular and effective approach for autonomous robots. The Raspberry Pi is a versatile single-board computer with ample processing power, memory, and connectivity options. It is well-suited for high-level tasks such as perception, decision-making, and communication. With its ability to run operating systems like Linux and frameworks like ROS (Robot Operating System), the Raspberry Pi provides a robust platform for implementing complex algorithms and managing the overall control of the autonomous system. On the other hand, Arduino boards are microcontrollers specifically designed for embedded systems and real-time control applications. They excel at low-level tasks, such as interfacing with sensors, reading inputs, and driving actuators. By utilizing an Arduino to control the motor driver, precise control over the robot's movements can be achieved. The integration of the Arduino, Raspberry Pi, ROS, LiDAR, and camera technologies in the autonomous inspection robot offers a comprehensive and robust solution for reliable and accurate data collection.

In this design, the knowledge of mechanical and electrical professional learning was fully exerted, that is, it involved the professional knowledge of mechanical part check selection, CAD drawing, etc., and also involved electrical engineering, single-chip microcomputer and other knowledge. The combination of mechanical and electrical enables me to fully and comprehensively integrate the knowledge I have learned into practice, and discover my own deficiencies and deficiencies in practice, make up for my own deficiencies by consulting materials, asking teachers and classmates, and improve my knowledge and professional qualities and skills as a mechanical and electrical student.

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